

A Mixed Method Study Assessing the Paulinian Remote Flexible Learning Experience

Alcher J. Arpilleda

Junior High School Assistant Principal, St. Paul University Surigao, Philippines

Sr. Marie Rosanne Mallillin, SPC

President, St. Paul University Surigao, Philippines

Abstract

To proactively respond to the challenges brought by the pandemic, St. Paul University Surigao implemented the Paulinian Remote Flexible Learning Experience (ReFLEx). Surveys have been carried out, but formal research has not been conducted to address identified strengths and areas for improvement. Thus, this study is conducted to assess the Paulinian ReFLEx in the Basic Education Department of the university. An explanatory sequential design was employed. Survey, interviews and tests were conducted to gather data. Frequency Count and Percentage Distribution, Mean and Standard Deviation, Kruskal-Wallis H test, Mann-Whitney U test, One-way Analysis of Covariance, and t-test were the statistical tools used in this study to analyze the quantitative data. Based on the findings revealed in this study, it was concluded that St. Paul University Surigao is implementing the Paulinian Remote Flexible Learning Experience (ReFLEx) excellently, where instructional processes, assessment methods, and student advancement programs were done synchronously or asynchronously in a blended learning mode. The Paulinian Remote Flexible Learning Experience (ReFLEx) is effective as a mode for the delivery of instruction. It is advised that the progress of implementation should be maintained while also resolving the identified issues. Expanding the scope allows for similar studies to be carried out.

Keywords: *explanatory sequential, experience, flexible learning, mixed method, remote.*

Suggested citation: Arpilleda, A.J., & Mallillin, M.R. (2025). A Mixed Method Study Assessing the Paulinian Remote Flexible Learning Experience. *European Journal of Contemporary Education and E-Learning*, 3(1), 32-40. DOI: 10.59324/ejceel.2025.3(1).03

Introduction

The emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic has reshaped life on a global scale, with profound implications for education systems worldwide (Louis-Jean & Cenat, 2020). The pandemic prompted governments to enforce stringent measures aimed at curbing virus transmission, leading to widespread school closures that disrupted traditional educational practices. In the Philippines, this disruption was marked by a community quarantine initiated on March 14, 2020, which resulted in an immediate halt to classes (Department of Education, 2020). Subsequently, Proclamation No. 929 was issued on

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

March 16, 2020, declaring a national state of calamity due to COVID-19 (Atienza, 2021).

As educational institutions grappled with these unprecedented challenges, they were compelled to rethink their instructional delivery methods. The closure of schools affected over 28 million Filipino learners as part of a staggering global total exceeding 1.2 billion students impacted by similar measures (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), 2020; Viner et al., 2020). In response to this crisis, the Department of Education called upon schools and universities to adapt swiftly and effectively. Education Secretary Briones articulated a clear mandate: "Education must continue even in times of crisis," underscoring the urgency of maintaining educational engagement.

To facilitate this continuity amid uncertainty, DepEd Order No. 12 series of 2020 was released, outlining a comprehensive Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan that embraced diverse learning modalities such as limited face-to-face classes and various forms of distance learning including online platforms and modular approaches. This shift represented a significant departure from conventional teaching methods and posed considerable challenges for educators who had relied heavily on in-person instruction.

In navigating these changes, St. Paul University Surigao (SPUS) demonstrated its commitment to educational excellence by implementing Online Distance Learning Education tailored to meet the needs of its students during this crisis. SPUS had been progressively integrating digital tools into its curriculum since 2012; thus, transitioning to full online distance learning in response to COVID-19 was a manageable leap for both students and faculty.

In pursuit of more inclusive instructional strategies during this period, SPUS introduced the Remote Flexible Learning Experience (ReFLEx), which combined synchronous and asynchronous learning modalities through various digital platforms. This innovative approach aimed not only to maintain educational continuity but also to foster student engagement in an increasingly digital landscape. To ensure that ReFLEx met its intended goals effectively over the past three years necessitated thorough assessment beyond regular surveys previously conducted.

This study aims to evaluate the implementation of ReFLEx within St. Paul University Surigao's Basic Education Department as it transitions into blended learning for the current academic year. As Junior High School Assistant Principal at SPUS, I recognize that insights gained from this assessment will be invaluable for future planning initiatives and program enhancements within our educational framework.

Materials and Methods

The researcher employed explanatory sequential design to gather information regarding assessing the Paulinian Remote Flexible Learning Experience (ReFLEx) in the Basic Education Department of St. Paul University Surigao. It involves a two-phase project in which the researcher collects quantitative data in the first phase, analyzes the results, and then uses the results to plan (or build on to) the second, qualitative phase. The quantitative results typically inform the types of participants to be purposefully selected for the qualitative phase and the types of questions that will be asked of the participants (Creswell, 2018). Descriptive research aims to accurately and systematically describe a population, situation, or phenomenon (McCombes,

2022). This design was deemed appropriate in this study because it will look into a specific subject, the assessment of Paulinian Remote Flexible Learning Experience, and it will also involve collecting data to test the hypothesis. However, in this study, the researcher used the qualitative responses to validate and confirm quantitative results, thus, using those as part of the discussion.

In addition, a Solomon Four Group Design was used to evaluate the effectiveness of Paulinian Remote Flexible Learning Experience. Figure 2 shows the flow of the design. Four groups were put into a test. In this design, two groups, experimental group A and control group B, were given pretests. After the pretest, Experimental Groups A and C were exposed to the Paulinian ReFLEEx where the four learning stations were used while Control Groups B and D were given a pure lecture only. A posttest was then conducted to all groups.

The respondents of this study were the Basic Education students, specifically the Junior High School Students. Four sections were sampled. The researcher chose Grade 9 students since they experienced ReFLEEx in both full online and blended learning mode. For the qualitative part, ten informants were interviewed. These informants were purposively chosen to ensure that they experienced ReFLEEx and they also took part in the survey conducted.

The researcher used three instruments in this study. For the quantitative part, an adapted questionnaire made by the Basic Education Academic Council in 2020 was used. The researcher added one part to collect the profile of the respondents. With this, the questionnaire consisted of two parts. Part 1 asked for the profile of the respondents. Part 2 of the questionnaire asked for the assessment of the Paulinian Remote Flexible Learning Experience in terms of *teachers' competence, class schedule, learning management system, and learning engagement*. The instrument's internal consistency is described as *excellent*, with 0.98 as the Cronbach alpha.

For the qualitative part, an in-depth interview on the informants' experiences on ReFLEEx was utilized to validate data gathered from the responses given in the questionnaire.

Lastly, to evaluate the effectiveness of the Paulinian Remote Flexible Learning Experience, a 24-item test was used and tested to four groups, following the Solomon Four Group Design.

In the analyzing the gathered data, the researchers used *Frequency Count and Percentage* to present the profile of the respondents, *Mean and Standard Deviation* to determine the level of assessment of the Paulinian Remote Flexible Learning Experience, *Kruskal-Wallis H test* to test the significant differences between respondent's age and their level of assessment of Paulinian Remote Flexible Learning Experience, *Mann-Whitney U test* to compare differences between the profile variables sex and device used and the level of assessment of Paulinian Remote Flexible Learning Experience, *One-way Analysis of Covariance* to determine whether there are any significant differences between experimental and control groups with pretest, and *t-test* to test differences on the posttest results of experimental and control groups without pretest.

Results and Discussion

This study aimed to assess the implementation of the Paulinian Remote Flexible Learning Experience (ReFLEEx) in the Basic Education Department of St. Paul

University Surigao. An explanatory sequential design was employed. The respondents of this study were the Basic Education students at St. Paul University Surigao. The main instruments used are a survey questionnaire and test for quantitative part and an in-depth interview for the qualitative part. Frequency Count and Percentage Distribution, Mean and Standard Deviation, Kruskal-Wallis H test, Mann-Whitney U test, One-way Analysis of Covariance, and t-test were the statistical tools used in this study to analyze the quantitative data.

Based on the analysis done on the data gathered, the findings revealed in this study are summarized as follows:

1. In terms of *age*, 92 (79.31%) respondents are 14 years old, then 15 years old with 18 (15.52%), and 13 years old with 6 (5.17%). In terms of *sex*, most of the respondents are females with 64 (55.17%) while 52 (44.83%) are males. In terms of *device used for learning*, most of the respondents used one device (mobile/ handheld device) with 99 (85.34%), while 17 (14.66%) used two (2) devices (mobile, laptops, etc.).

2. As to the Assessment of the Paulinian Remote Flexible Learning Experience in terms of *teacher's competence*, the item *My teachers are competent in handling blended learning (face-to-face and online classes)* got the highest mean ($\underline{M}=3.67$, $SD=0.51$), which can be verbally interpreted as *strongly agree* and qualitatively described as *excellent*. This means that the respondents experienced the competence of the teachers when it comes to handling classes, in different modalities. This is true because the Basic Education Faculty are given various training such as the month-long in-service training and continuous faculty development programs to equip themselves with suitable professional qualifications and pedagogical skills and strategies. This school year, the Basic Education Department sustained its implementation of the Remote Flexible Learning Experience using the blended learning modality, a combination of face-to-face and online classes.

Through ReFLEx and even with the challenges and limited resources, the teachers and students find ways to continue education, where creativity and innovativeness surface. As Kaiser and König (2019) stated, teacher competence is understood as context-specific, cognitive performance dispositions that are functionally responsive to situations and demands in certain domains. Professional development will be increasingly important for teachers in the digital age to stay abreast of quality and flexible education strategies for more sophisticated learners (Patterson, 2018).

Meanwhile, the item *My teachers willingly extend compassion and consideration to students who have difficulty with blended learning* got the lowest mean ($\underline{M}=3.51$, $SD=0.59$), which can be verbally interpreted as *strongly agree* and qualitatively described as *excellent*. Despite being the lowest indicator, it still yielded an excellent description, which means that the respondents experienced the compassion and consideration of the teachers despite some difficulties in learning.

As the University adapts to the new normal changes, the teachers continue to live the value of compassionate caring, especially when students have difficulty conducting online classes and complying with the tasks. They ensure that the students and parents are informed of their academic performance, progress, and all the necessary announcements and communications. They also address concerns of students and parents immediately and/or relay concerns to proper school authorities and promptly provide feedback. Changes and contingency plans in cases of poor internet connection, power outages, and other unavoidable events that are beyond the school's control are also communicated to parents and students.

Bartholomay (2021) stated that meeting students where they are during the pandemic requires compassion. Compassion entails hard work. Whenever the teacher extends help to the students who are in need, they also need to prepare materials to be given to the students as remediation or intervention, and that takes extra effort. During online classes, when teachers are disconnected from the meeting platform, he/ she needs to find ways to still continue or else, alternative activities will be given.

As to *class program / class schedule*, the items *With only four subjects per day, the current class program/class schedule allows us to focus more on the learning areas* and *With 4 days of academics and 1 day of non-academics, the current class program/schedule engages us with other equally essential activities that enhance our skills, abilities, talents, and performance* got the highest mean (\underline{M} =3.63, SD =0.60, and 0.58, respectively), which can be verbally interpreted as *strongly agree* and qualitatively described as *excellent*. This means that the respondents experienced a balanced and a more focused learning given the current class program/schedule. This school year, the Basic Education department allotted four days for academic and one day for non-academics. This set-up allows the students to have a balanced learning which contributes to their holistic formation. This engages them to develop their skills, abilities, talents, and performance through various academic and non-academic activities. With the current set-up, the high school students are given four subjects a day unlike what was practiced before the pandemic where eight subjects were given per day. As Grigorkevich et al. (2022) found, the distribution of the number of academic subjects per day contributes to sound academic schedule design. Thus, the students can focus more on the learning areas.

Meanwhile, the item *The current class program/class schedule is in sync with our bio-rhythm and provides enough time to prepare for our lessons* got the lowest mean (\underline{M} =3.45, SD =0.65), which can be verbally interpreted as *strongly agree* and qualitatively described as *excellent*. Despite being the lowest indicator, it still yielded an excellent description, which means that the respondents had a positive experience when it comes to the current schedule as they are prepared physically, mentally, emotionally, socially, and spiritually every day. A properly planned schedule of classes is important for online learning, which advantages students' self-organization (Grigorkevich et al., 2022). The class schedule should strictly designate breaks and free time, allowing students to be within certain limits and facilitating learning. Moreover, all classes have their daily morning routine where prayers, flag ceremony, reading of the gospel and institutional statements are given and recited. The advisers also give short reminders to help dispose class for the day.

Greater flexibility was viewed favourably by a majority of teachers, parents and students (Hood, 2020). There were accounts of greater flexibility enabling students to engage more deeply in tasks because they were able to dedicate extended periods of time to particular subjects and “catch-up” on other subjects at a later date.

As to *Quipper – Learning Management System*, the item *The Quipper orientation that is given once a year is sufficient* got the highest mean (\underline{M} =3.53, SD =0.64), which can be verbally interpreted as *strongly agree* and qualitatively described as *excellent*. This means that the respondents attended the students' orientation on the use of the Quipper, the official school learning management, and they found it sufficient. This is true because a week before the start of classes, orientation activities were conducted. Part of the academic orientation is the orientation and navigation of the LMS. Learning Management System (LMS), as defined by Aldiab et al. (2019), is a broad term that is used for a wide range of systems that organize and provide access to online learning services for students, teachers, and administrators.

The use of LMS is not new to the university since it has been utilized since 2018. Garcia et al. (2022) found that teachers highly utilized Quipper as Learning Management System in teaching in terms of Sending Assignments and Practice Examinations, Creating Educational Content, and Viewing and Downloading Analytics.

Meanwhile, the item *The Quipper staff answers query urgently and fix technicalities immediately* got the lowest mean ($\underline{M}=3.22$, $SD=0.67$), which can be verbally interpreted as *agree* and qualitatively described as *satisfactory*. Despite being the lowest indicator, it still yielded a satisfactory description, which means that although the respondents experienced technical difficulties in the use of the LMS, the staff is ready to assist their needs. SPUSurigao is assigned with one support staff that is handling all levels. When concerns arise, the teachers or advisers send the concern or query of the student to the staff.

As to *teaching - learning engagement* (ReFlex Stations), the items *The teacher-directed sessions are in-depth, comprehensive, and meaningful to achieve our target lessons* and *The overall conduct of the learning stations is logical, well-planned, and flexible and it gives us more time to submit quality output with the consultation time and expanded opportunity* got the highest mean ($\underline{M}=3.57$, $SD=0.64$, and 0.61 , respectively), which can be verbally interpreted as *strongly agree* and qualitatively described as *excellent*. This means that the respondents experienced an excellent implementation of the ReFLEEx where the learning stations made the learning flexible and where they have ample time to create and submit quality output. It was also noted from the findings that the teacher-directed session was rated excellent because in here, the students can interact with the teachers. They found it important as imparting knowledge and deepening the subject matter happen in this station. In this station, deepening further significant learning that students have acquired happens.

Meanwhile, the item *I am comfortable using the ReFlex pedagogy in our learning activities* got the lowest mean ($\underline{M}=3.30$, $SD=0.65$), which can be verbally interpreted as *strongly agree* and qualitatively described as *excellent*. Despite having the lowest mean indicator, it still yielded an excellent description, which means that the respondents felt at ease in using the ReFLEEx in learning. SPUS sustained its initiatives in providing a quality learning experience by adapting the Rotation Model. This ReFLEEx model utilizes four (4) teaching-learning stations: independent learning, collaborative learning, interactive teacher-directed learning, and assessment.

Learner engagement, as defined by Conway (2022), relates to student engagement where the degree of attention, curiosity, interest, optimism, and passion that students show when they are learning or being taught, which extends to the level of motivation they learn and progress in their education.

The respondents' assessment of the Paulinian Remote Flexible Learning Experience in the Basic Education Department is *excellent* with a mean rating of 3.52.

3. There was no statistically significant difference in the level of assessment of the Paulinian Remote Flexible Learning Experience based on the respondent's age, $\chi^2(2) = 2.084$, $p = 0.353$. This means that the age of the respondents does not matter as to how they experience and feel about the implementation of ReFLEEx. Any individual child might seem "more" mature in certain areas and "less" mature in others (Hansen, 2018). However, Simonds & Brock (2014) as cited by Oginni et al. (2021) reported that students' age and learning preference have a significant relationship.

There was a statistically significant difference in the level of assessment of the Paulinian Remote Flexible Learning Experience based on the respondent's sex ($z=-2.329$, $p =$

.020). This means that the sex of the respondents affects their experiences and feelings about the implementation of ReFLEEx. This is true because according to Hartono et al. (2019), there was a significant difference in student engagement level based on gender. In addition, Kovalik (2008) found that small group learning tends to work for girls because they are more comfortable asking the teacher for help if they need it. Female students were better at doing assignments, paying attention to educators during learning, preparing learning activities, and having better relationships with educators (Amir et al., 2014). In contrast, Garcia et al. (2022) found that the sex of the respondents does not affect the utilization of Quipper as Learning Management System.

There was no statistically significant difference in the level of assessment of the Paulinian Remote Flexible Learning Experience based on the respondent's device used ($z=-1.473$, $p = .141$). This means that the device used by the respondents does not affect their experiences and feelings about the implementation of ReFLEEx. This means that the whether the students used Mobile/ Handheld Devices or Computers/ Laptops, their experience is the same.

4. Experimental Group A and Control Group B got a *high* level in their mathematics achievement test ($M=17.16$, 17.06 , $SD=2.25$, 1.90 , respectively). Experimental Group A got a *very high* rating ($M=20.81$, $SD=1.62$), Experimental Group C also got a *very high* rating ($M=19.11$, $SD=3.49$). Meanwhile, Control Group B got a *high* rating ($M=17.88$, $SD=2.97$) and Control Group D also got a *high* rating ($M=16.68$, $SD=3.94$). It is evident with the result that the implementation of the Paulinian Remote Flexible Learning Experience is effective as the experimental groups performed significantly higher than the control groups. Arpilleda (2021) concluded in his study that the intervention materials gave a positive impact in mastering the least-learned competency identified as shown in the post-test results of the two groups. This is related to the present study because the researcher used an intervention, in the form of the learning stations, to the experimental groups, while no intervention was given to the control groups. Rosal et al. (2022) also found that there is a significant increase between the pretest and posttest scores after using an intervention.

5. There is a significant difference between the achievement of the experimental and control groups with pretest ($F(1, 58) = 28.340$, $p = .00001$). There is a significant difference between the mathematics achievement of the experimental and control groups without pretest, Experimental Group C and Control Group D (t -value = 3.043 , p -value= 0.003).

Conclusions

Based on the findings gathered, it is concluded that St. Paul University Surigao is implementing the Paulinian Remote Flexible Learning Experience (ReFLEEx) excellently, where instructional processes, assessment methods, and student advancement programs were done synchronously or asynchronously in a blended learning mode. The respondents' sex affects their experiences and feelings about the implementation of ReFLEEx, while age and device used do not. The intervention, in the form of the four learning stations, is effective in enhancing the mathematics achievement of the students. The Paulinian Remote Flexible Learning Experience (ReFLEEx) is effective as a mode for the delivery of instruction. This is evidenced by mathematics achievement. The experimental groups performed significantly higher

than the control groups, with or without pre-test. Thus, the four learning stations are well-implemented.

Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- Aldiab, A., Chowdhury, H., Kootsookos, A., Alam, F., & Allhibi, H. (2019). Utilization of Learning Management Systems (LMSs) in higher education system: A case review for Saudi Arabia. *Energy Procedia*, 160, 731-737.
- Amir, R., Saleha, A., Mohd Jelas, zalizan, Ahmad, A. R., & Hutkemri. (2014). Students ' Engagement by Age and Gender : A Cross-Sectional Study in Malaysia. *Middle East Journal of Scientific Research*, 21(10), 1886–1892. <https://doi.org/10.5829/idosi.mejsr.2014.21.10.85168>
- Arpilleda, A. J. (2021). Strategic intervention material: A tool in enhancing grade nine students' mathematical performance. *International Journal of Research*, 10(5), 61-72. <https://doi.org/10.5861/ijrse.2021.5051>
- Atienza, M. (2021, April 26). *The Philippines a Year under Lockdown Continuing Executive Dominance, Threats to Democracy, and Unclear Pandemic Response*. Verfassungsblog on Matters Constitutional. Retrieved from <https://verfassungsblog.de/the-philippines-a-year-under-lockdown/>
- Bartholomay, D. J. (2022). A time to adapt, not “return to normal”: Lessons in compassion and accessibility from teaching during covid-19. *Teaching Sociology*, 50(1), 62-72.
- Conway, A. (2022, January 5). *What is learner engagement and why is it important?* Freestone by Community Brands. Retrieved from <https://www.freestonelms.com/blog/what-is-learner-engagement/>
- Creswell, J.W., & Creswell, J.D. (2018). Mixed methods procedures. In, *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). Los Angeles, CA: SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Department of Education (2020). *DepEd Order No. 12 s. 2020 on the "Adoption of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan for School Year 2020-2021 in Light of the Covid-19 Public Health Emergency."* Retrieved from https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/DO_s2020_012.pdf
- Department of Education (2020). *Division Memorandum No. 341 s. 2020 on the Implementation of Modular Distance Learning with Television as Supplement*. Schools Division of Baybay City. Retrieved from <http://baybaycitydivision-deped.net/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/341-s.-2020-Implementation-of-Modular-Distance-Learning-with-Television-as-Supplement-MDL-TS.pdf>
- Garcia, R. C., Arpilleda, A. J., Mallillin, S. M. R., & Abadiano, M. N. (2022). Utilization of Quipper Application as Learning Management System in Teaching as Experienced by the Junior High School Teachers of St. Paul University Surigao. *International Journal of Science and Management Studies*, 5 (1), 129-142. <https://doi.org/10.51386/25815946/ijsms-v5i1p113>

- Grigorkevich, A., Savelyeva, E., Gaifullina, N., & Kolomoets, E. (2022). Rigid class scheduling and its value for online learning in higher education. *Education and Information Technologies*, 1-18.
- Hansen, J. (2018, June 13). *Why does age determine the how, what, and with whom of learning?* Education Reimagined. <https://education-reimagined.org/why-age/>
- Hartono, F. P., Umamah, N., Sumarno, R. P. N. P., & Puji, P. N. (2019). The level of student engagement based on gender and grade on history subject of senior high school students in Jember Regency. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, 8(8), 21-26.
- Hood, N. (2020). Learning from lockdown: What the experiences of teachers, students and parents can tell us about what happened and where to next for New Zealand's school system. *The Education Hub*.
- Kaiser, G., and König, J. (2019). "Competence Measurement in (Mathematics) Teacher Education and Beyond: Implications for Policy." *Higher Education Policy* 32: 597–615. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41307-019-00139-z>
- Kovalik, S. (2008, December). *Gender Differences and Student Engagement*. International Center for Leadership in Education. <https://nyctecenter.org/images/ctelibrary/files/research/Student%20Engagement%20and%20Gender%20white%20paper.pdf>
- Louis-Jean, J., & Cenat, K. (2020). Beyond the Face-to-Face Learning: A Contextual Analysis. *Pedagogical Research*, 5(4).
- McCombes, S. (2022, May 5). *Descriptive research design | Definition, methods & examples*. Scribbr. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/descriptive-research/>
- Oginni, A., Mogaji, E., & Nguyen, P. (2021). Reimagining the place of Physical Buildings in Higher Education in Developing Countries in a Post-COVID-19 Era. In E. gaji, J. Varsha, F. Maringe, & E. Hinson (Eds.), *Re-imagining Educational Futures in Developing Countries: Lessons from Global Health Crises*. Cham: Palgrave.
- Patterson, M.B. (2018). The forgotten 90%: Adult nonparticipation in education. *Adult Education Quarterly*, 68(1), 41 –62. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0741713617731810>
- Rosal, Gwyneth & Aguinaldo, Jhan & Reyes, Lean & Casuat, Gabriel & Balagtas, Romalyn & Mundo, Erickson. (2022). Improving the Least Mastered Competencies of Grade 11 Students in General Chemistry using Electronic Strategic Intervention Material (E-SIM). *KIMIKA*. 33. 59-76. <https://doi.org/10.26534/kimika.v33i2.59-76>
- Simonds, T., & Brock, B. (2014). Relationship Between Age, Experience, and Student Preference for Types of Learning Activities in Online Courses. *The Journal of Educators Online*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.9743/jeo.2014.1.3>
- St. Paul University Surigao – The PauliGlobe (2020). *Paulinian ReFLEx Primer* [Infographic]. Facebook.
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (2020). *COVID-19 Educational Disruption and Response*. Retrieved from <https://en.unesco.org/covid19/educationresponse>
- Viner, R. M., Russell, S. J., Croker, H., Packer, J., Ward, J., Stansfield, C., ... Booy, R. (2020). School closure and management practices during coronavirus outbreaks including COVID-19: A rapid systematic review. *The Lancet Child & Adolescent Health*, 4(5), 397-404. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2352-4642\(20\)30095-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2352-4642(20)30095-X)

